

A general view of task-based approach to teaching language

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Abstract

More teachers across all subject areas have been exploring ways to improve the conventional modes of instruction in recent years. They have sought at strategies for making the classroom more student-centered and have delved into the various ways that students might take more initiatives in learning and knowledge processing. Task-based Approach (TBA) is one of them. This paper endeavors to introduce its theoretical bases, teaching principles, teaching procedures and evaluations to present a general idea about TBA to teaching language.

Keywords: Task-based approach; cognitive theory; social interaction; tasks.

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Introduction

The task-based approach to language teaching is a more recent theory that is based on the research of psychologists and linguists (Willis, 1996). Language acquisition has traditionally been thought of as the process of establishing a series of structures, each one making on the one before, such as from sounds to words, from words to sentences. Using the task-based approach, learning is seen as a series of communicative tasks, with communication and engagement typically organized around various tasks rather than in terms of vocabulary or grammar (Liu & Guo, 2020; Liu et al., 2021). In class, students are expected to perform tasks in the target language that they might also need to do beyond the classroom. Through learning tasks that are created to involve learners in the real, active, and simple use of language for significant purposes, TBA seeks to give the learners opportunity to connect with and discover both oral and written language.

This paper seeks to answer the question: what is Task-Based Approach? As there are many conflicting theories and the empirical data does not offer definitive answers, there is no straightforward approach to respond to this.

Theoretical Bases

The task-based approach, the most recent advancement in communicative language teaching, first appeared in the 1980s. The task-based approach may be attributed to American philosopher John Dewey, who laid the intellectual groundwork for task-based language teaching. *Designing Tasks for the Communicative Classroom* was published by Nunan in 1989. Some people regard this book as a turning point in task-based language teaching. Task-based learning expanded in popularity in the 1990s, especially in England. *A Framework for Task-based Learning*, a monograph by Jane Willis, was released in 1996. It was useful for both task-based and non-task-based teaching.

Dewey's pragmatism emphasized learning by doing over rote learning. Learning by doing is one of central principles of TBLT. According to Willis (1996), we can create projects that our students would find interesting to complete and that would promote the kind of interaction they might need to have for each topic or material. Nunan (1989) asserts that a communicative task is a type of classroom project that helps students to understand, utilize, create, or draw attention in the target language while concentrating on using their grammatical expertise to convey content rather than modify form. Richards and Rodgers (2014) thought that the linking of functional view of language to cognitive theory generated the communicative approach which spawned off off-shoots such as task-based language teaching in the learner-centered education.

Ellis (2003) argues that cognitive science serves as the foundation for task-based curricula developed by second language acquisition (SLA) scholars. The significance of learner engagement is highlighted, and the theoretical underpinning is that task-based instruction needs to be well-suited with the cognitive processes required in L2 acquisition. As long as they present a reasonable challenge, tasks will be engaging and motivating (Ellis, 2003).

What is more is that task-based syllabus is 'psycholinguistic' which means "that it is based on interactional categories that have been shown to affect the opportunities learners have and to modify their own output" (Ellis, 2003). Therefore, from the above famous linguists and educators, we can safely infer the following: Task-based language teaching is one way among many to carry out communicative language teaching. It lays stress on learning by doing and develops on the basis of some psychological theories and social constructivist theory.

I. Psychological theory

1. Interactive hypothesis:

One of the conditions in language learning is "comprehensible input" which can be "triggered" by interaction. When learners try to complete their tasks, they need to communicate with others. In this course, messages are received and transferred when much attention are paid to the meanings. This course may be accompanied by inquiry, questioning or explanation. That will trigger more input and output. It is "meaning negotiation" (Long, 1996). Interactive theory considers that task can supply the learners with two comprehensive and balanced systems to help them notice the meaning of the language and the form of the language at the same time (Mishra, 2005). But "meaning negotiation" cannot necessarily develop the learners' grammar system.

2. Cognitive theory:

Skehan's (1998) cognitive approach considers that we should understand the role of task through human's memorizing and utilizing of language. There are two different systems in the process of manipulating and utilizing language: exemplar-based and rule-based systems. The former is characterized by vocabulary, including scrap language, vocabulary and ready-made formulaic chunks of language, which is called by Skehan's structured and exemplar-based learning. Exemplar-based system actually refers to some ready-made collocations used by learners in the quick response in conversation (e.g., Not at all, Never mind, That's fine). Language is simple to be learned and used. However, rule-based system should have the reliability of language and social decency. With the need of a longer time to learn and process, it is suitable in the language activities which are easier to control and have less demands of fluency. Skehan's theory supplies an important studying field – the relationship between task and language acquisition. Researchers can study which kind task arouses the learners' more attention to the language fluency and accuracy. Skehan (1998) also thinks that maybe different types of tasks cause the learners to gain different language competence.

II. Social interaction theory

This theory emphasizes that human's learning and development happen in the interaction with others. Learning is closely linked to feelings about oneself. Interaction with other people facilitates learning in a social situation. According to a great number of research papers of language acquisition, the way to learn a language is mainly through the communication with others. Because the learner's language system is developed through communication activities with certain purposes, the key problem of learning a language is to supply the learners a great deal of interaction / communication chances. Interaction is that learners pay their attention to utilize language to express and receive authentic information.

From the above, we can see that because of the relationship with Communicative Approach, the Task-based Approach take psychological and social constructivist theory as its theoretical bases. But cognitive theory, social interaction theory and interactive hypothesis are those which contribute more to Task-based Approach. Through cognitive theory, we know what kind of task we should plan according to the levels and the demands of the learners. The core idea of social interaction theory and interactive hypothesis is that language can be achieved through interaction and communication which is just what Task-based Approach advocates.

Teaching Principles

There are no authorized and accepted teaching principles about Task-based Approach, but some internationally influential researchers and educators of English as a Second Language (ESL) have brought forth their own teaching principles, for example, Nunan (1989), Long (1996), Willis (1996), Skehan (1998), and Ellis (2003). All of them elaborated on the teaching principles from different aspects, but they agree on some points:

1. **The student-centered principle:** Task-based Language Teaching (TBLT) endeavors to promote a student-centered learning environment in which a need to learn based on positive respect and shared trust will be stimulated.
2. **The form-function principle:** In order to learn to do things with language, the learners should make clear the relationship between language form and language function. The design of task should take the combination of language form, function and meaning into account and enable the learners to grasp the language form as well as the ability to use language properly in teaching the language that make forms and functional relationships transparent.
3. **The authenticity principle:** The introduction of authentic texts into the learning situation. The linguistic materials that learners deal with are authentic tasks. The research has found that students pay more attention to the issues which closely relate to their daily life. A natural, authentic, or stimulant authentic situation should be created for learners to experience and master language. Learning is life and life is also learning.
4. **The task dependency principle:** Each activity in a lesson acts as a step on a pedagogical ladder, allowing the learner to develop to highly complex levels of communicative performance.
5. **Learning by doing:** Students are inspired to achieve their potential when they learn by doing. Although they still need to find out the grammar and memorize vocabulary, learners grasp the language by speaking it in class. Also, this principle includes an interaction principle, where they have the same core idea: doing tasks communicatively, but the latter is more specific.
6. **Scaffolding principle:** It involves "setting up" the environment to facilitate the learner's entry and success, then gradually regaining control and giving the function over to the learner as he or she acquires the necessary skills (Zhao, 2015).

All the principles are important in carrying out TBLT in language classroom. Implementing these principles can guarantee language learning happens in an authentic, interactional, active, natural and student-centered environment, and help learners develop their language competence and knowledge as well (Wang, 2009).

The language learning under these principles will be interesting not boring. Learners easily acquire language by communicating and interacting with purpose while performing tasks and activities.

Teaching Procedures

I. Task

Task is a key concept in TBLT, only after making clear the meaning of task can we probe into the teaching procedures of TBLT.

1. Definition of task:

Different exponents gave different definitions to task. An action that is carried out as a result of organizing language is referred to as a task (Richards & Schmidt, 2014). A task is an activity in which “*the target language is used by the learner for a communicative purpose in order to achieve an outcome*” (Willis, 1996, as cited in Shirisha et al., 2017). The communicative task is a type of classroom assignment that enables students to comprehend, produce, interact, or manipulate the target language while focusing on using their grammatical expertise to express content rather than modify form. The task must feel accomplished and be capable of functioning alone as a cohesive, complete communication (Nunan, 1989).

In task-based learning (TBL), tasks are usually activities where the learner utilizes the target language for communication to achieve a goal, with the emphasis on exchanging meanings rather than developing particular language forms.

2. Characteristics of task:

By representing a broad consensus among educators and scholars and proposing five defining criteria, Skehan (1998) in his book *A Cognitive Approach to Language Learning* establishes a solid foundation for task definition from a pedagogical perspective.

1. The meaning is primary;
2. There is a goal which needs to be worked towards;
3. The activity is outcome-evaluated;
4. There is a real-world relationship;
5. Its primary task is completed.

II. Teaching procedures:

The general teaching procedures of the Task-based Approach are:

1. Pre-task phase

The pre-task phase has four objectives: to offer new language that learners can use to complete the task, to mobilize already-existing linguistic resources, to reduce the cognitive load, and to encourage learners to render tasks in more difficult ways. The topic is introduced, the students are given thorough instructions on what must be done during the task stage, and the teacher may even help the students remembering specific language that may be useful for the activity. Oftentimes during the pre-task period, a record of the task being completed by others is played. Students may now clearly see what is expected of them. They may take the necessary time to study and take notes.

1. **Warm-up:** To mobilize the existing background knowledge.
2. **Introduction of new language materials:** When input new language materials, we should relate it to learners' existing study experiences and supply the thinking clues and directions for the learners.
3. **Presentation of vocabulary and grammar structure:** Present new language (e.g., functions, grammar, vocabulary, phonology, discourse features) in the authentic or approximate authentic situation, and check the new language that has been understood, as well as records of new language learnt.
4. **Providing a model:** Asking students to observe a model in performing the task with new words and expressions which, if necessary, the teacher will explain them. The cognitive load on the learner can be alleviated just by watching others execute a task.
5. **Imitation and rehearsal:** Performing a similar task can improve the language fluency and accuracy.

2. During-task / while-task phase:

On the base of pre-task phase, this phase is the main acquisition process. In this process, the teacher should encourage learners to reconstruct their language as well as improve their language fluency and accuracy.

1. **Planning / strategic planning:** Students have adequate time to plan, are given instructions on what and how to plan, and work individually rather than in groups (Ellis, 2003; Markee & Kunitz, 2013). Planning includes decision-making, agreeing, and suggesting (Ortega, 2005).
2. **Task implementing:** Tasks can be carried out individually, in pairs, or in groups. In this procedure, language competence will be stressed. Task completing is primary.
3. **Reporting:** Give students opportunity to report their findings and explore their achievements by concluding or making inferences.

3. Post-task phase:

This process offers the chance to complete the activity again, promotes reflection on how the work was performed, and draws attention to form.

1. Learners go over the process of completing task.
2. Learners reflect and analyze their own mistakes and problems.
3. Teacher classifies, analyzes the tasks, and help learners enforce the language knowledge.

This is a process emphasizes language focus, practice, and works on language items that may have happened or been required during the task. From the above, we can see that the procedures of task-based language learning include task and non-task activities, stressing both the language knowledge and language competence. In pre-task and post-task phases, the focus will be on forms while in the while-task phase, it will be on form (long). The pre-task phase prepares for the while-task, and it is the vital phase in the whole teaching process on which the success of the teaching is founded. If this phase is well organized and carried out, in the next phase, task will probably be successfully implemented, and ideal effects can be achieved.

If not, the main tasks will probably fail, and proper effects cannot be achieved. Besides, when we design tasks, we should take many factors into consideration such as the levels of learners and the authenticity of the task situation.

Evaluation of Task-based Approach

I. Advantages:

1. Unlike a Presentation, Practice, and Production (PPP) approach, there are no language restrictions on students. Instead of only practicing one pre-selected topic in each of the three levels, they must use all of their linguistic resources.
2. From the students' interactions with the language, a natural context that is unique and appropriate to them is created. PPP requires the creation of situations; some of which can be incredibly unnatural, in order to communicate the language.
3. With TBL, learners' exposure to language will be significantly more varied. They will be exposed to a wide variety of linguistic structures, collocations, and patterns.
4. The language that is studied is a result of what the students need. Instead of the teacher or the course book making the decision, this requirement decides what will be covered in the lesson.
5. Students spend a great deal of time engaging in this approach, which emphasizes communication. Comparatively, PPP lessons appear to be more teacher-centered. Simply keep an eye on how much time students spend exchanging ideas throughout a task-based class.
6. It is motivating and pleasant (Herrera Núñez & Núñez Ospina, 2005).

II. Disadvantages:

1. Sometimes in collaborative work such as group work or pair work, some learners will probably provide lower level language models, or even some learners "practice" their mother tongue instead of what they are supposed to do, or the learners are carried away and cause problems of class control. All of those will cause low classroom teaching efficiency.
2. The teacher must use a great deal of initiative and creativity when using task-based learning. Task-based learning may not be possible if the teachers are constrained to more traditional duties or do not have the time or resources to implement it.
3. Evaluation and feedback of task-based learning may be strenuous. Task-based learning cannot be measured by some of the more constrained and conventional tests because of the way it works.

Conclusion

The task-based approach offers a departure from the grammatical practice patterns that have historically failed to help many learners learn how to speak. It can be viewed as one specific way to put the more general "communicative approach" into practice. It encourages students to try with whatever English they may still remember, to try new things out fearlessly in front of others, and to take an active role in their own learning both within and outside the classrooms. It also provides the learners a great deal of authentic language input and output, activate learners' innate learning motivation.

In the process of completing tasks, learners can comprehensively utilize the language they learn and pay their attention to the meaning of the language not just the language form, develop their language competence and performance as well (Hautemo, 2019).

The application of a new teaching model does not mean the total abandoning of traditional teaching models. We need to combine the reasonable and effective parts of traditional methods and new methods. There are many problems waiting to be solved in the future teaching practice. We need to put more efforts to study the theoretical bases and principles of TBA, apply it into our Chinese teaching, and serve our Chinese learners.

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